

PRODIGEES

*Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe
Towards Sustainable Development*

D4.3 Semi-annual Project Newsletter

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Project Newsletter

The Online Newsletter provided information on the project regularly. Originally conceptualised as a semi-annual compilation shared centrally, in the implementation the project management benefitted from communicating about the project and disseminating its results on a more regular basis. In this context, the communication approach foresaw to have every secondment research featured in a newsletter entry. Newsletter entries illustrated secondment frameworks, institutions and locations, research processes and results, network-wide events and presentations, and science communication tools, like short videos.

The Project Newsletter contributed to achieving four objectives of Work Package (WP) 4 on Exploitation, Dissemination, and Network Sustainability:

- To implement the Dissemination and Communication Strategy for maximum outreach via target-group specific channels
- To exploit the project results through international participatory multi-stakeholder Policy Labs to generate Policy Briefs that provide advice to promote policy paths more likely to maximise benefits of digitalisation for sustainability
- To exploit the project results for Transnational Open Access Training with multiple network institutions which translates and employs R&I activities for students, trainers, and institutions active in capacity-development

- To ensure long-term impact of R&I results and the sustainability of the network in a permanent collaboration framework.

The following table lists newsletter entries by date, incl. URL.

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14 December 2020	PRODIGEES – Research, Training, and Staff Exchange on Digitalisation and Sustainability amid Covid-19
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23 February 2023	PRODIGEES project: between a laboratory and a business school in Brazil
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28 March 2023	Research stay in Jakarta: IDOS researcher Benjamin Stewart looks at Open Science in relation to science policy
04 April 2023	Building Climate Resilience in Urban Informal Settlements through Data Co-production

25 April 2023	Postgraduate Training Programme: Brazil Research Team evaluates data in Bonn
28 June 2023	PRODIGEES research exchanges at IDOS
21 August 2023	T20 Side Event “Utopias for Global Cooperation: Toward joint visions for Global Digital Commons”
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17 April 2024	Constructive communication in the fake news era
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29 May 2024	Joint Conference of the National School of Government of South Africa and MGG
15 July 2024	Brazil, South Africa & the Ban on Huawei
08 September 2024	The EU and Forest Protection
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10 December 2024	Interview: In a digitalized world, who has the right to the city?
16 December 2024	PRODIGEES 2024: Bridging Digitalisation and Sustainability Through Research and Innovation Staff Exchanges
23 January 2025	Integration of mass transit systems: IDOS researcher’s Fellowship at CSIS in Jakarta
24 February 2025	MGG/PRODIGEES Prepares for Its Final Conference in Mexico City
24 March 2025	Reflecting on digitalisation in the public sector in Mexico City
26 March 2025	PRODIGEES @ CSIS
27 March 2025	MGG/PRODIGEES Final Conference: Experts discussed digitalisation and sustainability

Annex: Examples of PRODIGEES Project Newsletter Entries

PRODIGEES – Research, Training, and Staff Exchange on Digitalisation and Sustainability amid Covid-19

By Newsletter | 14. Dezember 2020 | Category: From the Institute, Training |

Logo: PRODIGEES, DIE

Staff exchange projects are amongst the casualties of 2020's pandemic lockdowns and travel restrictions. The *Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development (PRODIGEES)* (www.prodigees.info) project proves to be a powerful and encouraging exception. PRODIGEES, which receives funding from the European Union through Horizon 2020's Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action, Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (MSCA-RISE), is coordinated by DIE, harnessing its Managing Global Governance (MGG) network to strengthen knowledge cooperation between Europe and non-European research institutes. PRODIGEES' value was highlighted in an issue of DIE's [Current Column](#) in April 2020.

PRODIGEES hosted its kickoff meeting on 30th March, coinciding with the lockdown measures being imposed across Europe. Instead of taking place in Berlin, the conference was hosted virtually, balancing time zones and new conferencing etiquette. This gave the project's Steering Committee the ability to take immediate action. Within two months the Consortium agreed to adapt the original secondment plan, onboard new partners, and thereby mitigate the risks posed by the national and international reactions to COVID-19. DIE contacted PRODIGEES' Project Officer in Brussels, setting in motion a contingency plan to stabilise the project through the uncertainties of the pandemic.

Before the initial lockdown, PRODIGEES piloted its program in January with a research secondment performed by Prof. Dr. Ingrid Schneider of the University of Hamburg. While the pandemic brought exchanges to a standstill, the PRODIGEES team used Prof. Schneider's experience to further develop its programme. Since then, the Steering Committee has postponed all secondments until 2021, with the exception of two researchers arriving to Germany from Instituto Mora in Mexico City. Still, PRODIGEES hosted an event in October for its Transnational Open Access Training, taking the form of an academic module on Sustainable Digitalisation for DIE's virtual MGG Academy.

Research on sustainable digitalisation is imperative, as more of our work and social lives take place online, and as the pandemic exploits inequalities around the globe. Data privacy and protection is a topic of strong concern, with each country and each organization deciding for themselves how to balance efficiency and convenience with privacy and security. Ingrid Schneider's PRODIGEES publication, "[Democratic Governance of Digital Platforms and Artificial Intelligence?](#)", speaks to the power struggle between regional models of data procurement and ownership.

Data privacy is only one of the project's subject areas. PRODIGEES research is split between two main work packages, "Governance and Society" and "Economy and Environment". These wide umbrellas inspire a diverse range of research topics with local to global foci. Topics range from big data collection in India, blockchain use in Brazil, the Internet of Things for sustainable development in Indonesia, artificial intelligence in climate mitigation and the list goes on among over 80 different research projects.

The 'digital divide' was the theme of Dr. Carlos Dominguez' PRODIGEES research when he seconded to Germany from Instituto Mora this fall. In lieu of Horizon 2020's pandemic regulations, and due to DIE's own coronavirus measures, Dr. Dominguez came to Germany but did not perform all of his research within the halls of DIE. As most of DIE staff, he performed his research partly remotely and converted his PRODIGEES workshop, "[Digital, but still Unequal: the challenges of digitalisation for emerging powers – Mexico](#)" into a virtual workshop. The virtual workshop used social theories to explore the concept of the 'digital divide' in categories such as capital, education, labor skills and cultural production. Using innovative tools such as Zoom's breakout rooms and Mural's collaborative boards, Dr. Dominguez demonstrated the power of digitalisation in overcoming some of the barriers raised by COVID-19.

The coronavirus may have impeded PRODIGEES' initial momentum, but the European Commission's flexibility for Horizon 2020 projects allowed the quick-acting network to retain the integrity of its mission.

In an age when digital tools hold great promise and great risk, and when a pandemic has made us all more digitally dependent, PRODIGEES research remains more pertinent and more necessary than ever.

New online event series by EU network PRODIGEES on digitalisation and climate change

By Newsletter | 27. Januar 2021 | Category: Event

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The Horizon2020 research and network project [PRODIGEES](#), coordinated by the German Development Institute / Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik (DIE) and implemented with partners from the [Managing Global Governance \(MGG\) Network](#), kicked off a collaborative [online event series](#) with the Centre international de formation européenne (CIFE).

The first two virtual events on 10 December 2020 and 21 January 2021 with Dr Simone Lucatello, from Instituto Mora in Mexico City, focused on the intersection between digitalisation and climate change and thereby addressed one of the key research areas of PRODIGEES (Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe towards Sustainable Development). On the basis of an overview of the challenges of climate change and an introduction of the reports by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), Dr Lucatello highlighted digitalisation's role in carbon creation. At the same time, he illustrated the power of digitalisation for climate protection, for instance in relation to energy efficiency, agriculture practices, mobility and transportation, climate education or as a tool for climate scientists. Dr Lucatello is a social scientist with a research focus on climate change and sustainability. His collaborations include projects with the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), United Nations Information Centres (UNIC) und United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) as well as the Inter-American Development Bank (IADB).

The webinar series is planned to continue later this year.

All developments can be followed on the PRODIGEES website: www.prodigees.info.

Online event series by MGG Network, PRODIGEES and CIFE continued

By Newsletter | 24. Februar 2021 | Category: Event

The Managing Global Governance (MGG) Network and its EU-funded research initiative on digitalisation and sustainable development PRODIGEES continued its collaboration with the Centre international de formation européenne (CIFE) in February with a [presentation](#) "Digital but still Unequal: Challenges of Smart Technologies from a Comparative Perspective" by Dr. Juan Carlos Dominguez of Instituto Mora in Mexico City. Dr. Dominguez, an alumnus of the MGG Academy and key partner for both PRODIGEES and the MGG Network, encouraged participants to reflect on the degree to which the international development agenda lags behind technological advancement. At the same time, he advocated for caution, claiming that science and technology are not the "magical bullets" to solve all global problems.

Dr. Dominguez' presentation continues a PRODIGEES-CIFE online event series which began with Instituto Mora's Dr. Simone Lucatello in a discussion about the intersection between digitalisation and climate change.

More information about the series, including recordings of past presentations, can be found on [CIFE's Executive Trainings web page](#).

For more information about the PRODIGEES project, please consult our website at www.prodigees.info.

©Juan Carlos Dominguez

Exchange between Mexico City and Bonn

By Newsletter | 29. November 2021 | Category: Allgemein

Within the PRODIGEES project, Instituto Mora in Mexico City and DIE in Bonn have exchanged research staff for advancing cooperation and transnational knowledge in the field of digitalisation.

Dr. Simone Lucatello from Instituto Mora – a Mexican Public Research Centre and member of the PRODIGEES (Promoting Research On Digitalisation In Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development) network – joined the German Development Institute / Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik (DIE) for a visiting period. He studied and deepened the research on the impacts of digitalisation across the environmental dimension of sustainable development, climate change and its governance. Dr. Lucatello engaged in several meetings and interviews with colleagues at DIE as well as other international institutions in Bonn and elsewhere. At the beginning of 2021 and under the same project, Dr. Lucatello offered a talk on climate change and digitalisation, as part of the research activities that can be found on the [PRODIGEES website](#).

Open Science: a transformative paradigm

[Benjamin Stewart](#), a research associate and PRODIGEES project manager at DIE, as well as doctoral student with the University of Bonn, joined Instituto Mora. He investigates how the implementation of UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Science institutionalises the use of digital technologies and online networks in research and higher education institutes. Open Science is a transformative paradigm for how the scientific community thinks about and does science, addressing questions of inclusion and transparency, and posing challenges to science policy and sustainable development. Stewart conducted interviews with staff members of Instituto Mora, the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM), commentators for the Permanent Mission of Mexico to UNESCO, UNESCO's Open Science Advisory Committee, among other organisations. The preliminary results of Stewart's work were demonstrated in the workshop, "Open Science: Epistemologies, science policy implementation and digitalisation", which can be found in [PRODIGEES' comprehensive repository on Zenodo](#) along with the work of Dr. Lucatello. The research staff exchange lasted from September to December 2021.

Transnational knowledge cooperation

PRODIGEES, a project funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 research programme, is an instrument for catalysing ongoing research in digitalisation towards sustainable development, and for invigorating knowledge cooperation networks between advanced and emerging economies, specifically those countries with a history of partnership in DIE's [Managing Global Governance \(MGG\) network](#). The project is a Marie Skłodowska Curie Action – Research & Innovation Staff Exchange (MSCA-RISE), the basis of which is the exchange of research staff between partners. Travel restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic have all but halted staff exchanges for all Horizon 2020 MSCA-RISE projects since March 2020. However, now that vaccination rates are increasing world-wide, staff exchanges are beginning again, fulfilling their promise of transnational knowledge cooperation.

PRODIGEES Workshop "Digitalization and Sustainable Development – Enabling Narratives Towards a Green Digital Transformation"-EN

By Newsletter | 30. Mai 2022 | Category: Allgemein

Digitalization and Sustainable Development: ENABLING NARRATIVES TOWARDS A GREEN DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

©DIE

The COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated the great potential of digitalisation for societies and economies, e.g. for access to education or with new impulses for technological and economic innovation. At the same time, many world regions struggle to seize the opportunities given the rebound effects related to energy consumption and a deepening digital divide. During his month-long research secondment to Instituto Mora in Mexico City in the framework of the [Managing Global Governance \(MGG\) network's PRODIGEES project](#), [Wulf Reiners](#) (German Development Institute / Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik (DIE)) has discussed competing narratives of digitalisation and their impact on digitalisation strategies with experts from academia and the private sector in the Mexican context. The exchange was carried out as a face-to-face workshop with online streaming in coordination between DIE, the [Instituto de Investigaciones Dr. José María Luis Mora](#) and [Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit \(GIZ\)](#) through its ["Digital Transformation Centre in Mexico"](#) (DTC).

PRODIGEES conferences „The 2030 Agenda and International Training for the Public Sector“

By Newsletter | 30. Mai 2022 | Category: Allgemein

©DIE, Mexican and international conference participants and members of the MGG network in the Mexican Congress

With the [conference](#) "The 2030 Agenda and International Training for the Public Sector" in Mexico City, the ["Managing Global Governance" \(MGG\)](#) network has continued its peer exchange on [capacity development for the 2030 agenda with the public sector](#). The conference brought together representatives from research and training institutions, politics and public administration, the private sector and civil society organisations from Brazil, Germany, India, Indonesia, Mexico, South Africa and international organisations such as the United Nations System Staff College (UNSSC). It was carried out in collaboration between the German Development Institute / Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik (DIE) and the Mexican Chamber of Deputies, the National School of Public Administration of Brazil (ENAP), and Instituto Mora (Mexico). The conference served four purposes. First, it provided a public, high-level forum on the 2030 agenda for sustainable development in Mexico. Second, the discussion between decision-makers and international representatives from national schools of public administration (SPAs) highlighted the role of the public sector and the role of training institutions for the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Third, a hybrid peer-exchange [workshop](#) shed light on the competences needed for transformative policy-making, training programmes for local leadership and the combination of learning online and in-person. Finally, the cooperation amongst SPAs and further training institutions closed with a 2-day planning workshop to set out a roadmap for future activities. The recording of the live-streamed parts of the conference can be found [online](#). The initiative, based on the ["New York Programme of Action"](#) as developed during a joint [HLPF Side Event 2018](#), was carried out in cooperation with the EU Horizon2020 project [PRODIGEES](#).

PRODIGEES project: visiting scholars at IDOS

By Newsletter | 25. August 2022 | Category: Allgemein

©IDOS

Dr Francisco Javier Porras Sánchez was a guest at IDOS in July and August 2022. His work explores understandings of digitalization among different stakeholder groups in Mexico and Germany. His home institution, [Instituto Mora](#), is a leading Mexican research centre of the National Council of Science and Technology of Mexico (CONACYT), specialising in history, social sciences, and international cooperation. It also serves as co-coordinator of the PRODIGEES (*Promoting Research on Digitisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development*) project.

Dr Amit Kumar is focusing on EU and Indian strategies for inclusive digital transformation during his two-month research stay in Bonn. His home institution, [Research and Information System for Developing Countries \(RIS\)](#), is an autonomous policy research institution in New Delhi, supported by the Indian Ministry of External Affairs, that fosters policy dialogue on international development cooperation, economic development, trade, investment, technology and governance.

In addition, from the MGG team, [Eva Lynders](#) will be seconded to the [Centre for Strategic and International Studies \(CSIS\)](#) in Jakarta from August to September 2022 to carry out PRODIGEES research on digital networks and collaboration. As part of her secondment, she will also organise a joint side event of CSIS and IDOS during the T20 Summit.

All activities take place between partner institutions of the MGG network, from which the PRODIGEES project emerged with IDOS as the lead coordinator. It enables the exchange of research and innovation staff between institutions in Brazil, the EU, India, Indonesia, Mexico and South Africa with over 80 individual research projects to be carried out from January 2020 to June 2025.

More information about PRODIGEES events, news and publications can be found at www.prodigees.info.

ADMINISTRATION

FGV EBAPE is only South American institution to form partnership with Germany in digital area

The initiative is represented in Brazil by FGV EBAPE, and it also has partners in Germany, Italy, Mexico, South Africa, Indonesia and India.

13/09/2022

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Fundação Getúlio Vargas' Brazilian School of Public and Business Administration (FGV EBAPE) has formed a partnership with Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe towards Sustainable Development (PRODIGEES), a project run by the German government. The initiative promotes international collaboration and the sharing of knowledge on global governance and key issues around digitization in support of the goals of the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

In Brazil, PRODIGEES' manager is Professor Roberto Pimenta, the head of FGV EBAPE's Center for Academic Education and Research, while its coordinator is Professor Juliana Mansur. The project involves the exchange of knowledge, whereby the school's professors and researchers take their academic and scientific perspectives abroad and foreign professors share their experiences in Brazil.

"The main objective of the project is to generate a better understanding of digital transformation processes and exponential technologies, as well as their impacts on sustainable development in different regions of the world," says Professor Mansur.

The initiative is represented in Brazil by FGV EBAPE, and it also has partners in Germany, Italy, Mexico, South Africa, Indonesia and India.

Side Event zu “Utopias of Global Cooperation” beim T20-Gipfel Indonesien 2022

By Newsletter | 27. September 2022 | Category: Allgemein

T20 ist eine offizielle G20-Engagement-Gruppe, die führende Denkfabriken und Forschungseinrichtungen zusammenbringt, um forschungsbasierte Politikempfehlungen zu geben. Die Initiative wurde in Zusammenarbeit mit dem [PRODIGEES-Projekt](#) des MGG-Netzwerks durchgeführt.

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„Utopie“ ist kein üblicher Begriff für Wissenschaftler*innen, wenn es nicht darum geht, zu verdeutlichen, dass es für etwas keinerlei wissenschaftliche Evidenz gibt oder dass es aus den Modellen, die wir verwenden, um Annahmen über zukünftige Entwicklungen zu treffen, nicht abgeleitet werden kann. Einige von uns haben den Satz „Das ist utopisch!“ möglicherweise in der Vergangenheit schon verwendet, um auszudrücken, dass eine Idee keiner weiteren Betrachtung wert ist. Was aber, wenn Utopien – oder positive Zukunftsvisionen, die aus heutiger Sicht unrealistisch erscheinen mögen – genau das sind, was wir brauchen, um gemeinsam neue „social imaginaries“ zu entwickeln – gemeinsame Bilder davon, wie wir leben könnten, die das Potenzial haben, globale Zusammenarbeit zu leiten?

Unterstützt durch methodische Elemente von CoCreAct und Backcasting haben einige Teilnehmer*innen des T20-Gipfels 2022 gemeinsam positive Zukunftsvisionen entwickelt, die neue Formen der globalen Zusammenarbeit inspirieren könnten. Den Auftakt der Veranstaltung am 5. Und 6. September bildeten zwei inspirierende Kurzvorträge von Prof. Anna-Katharina Hornidge, Direktorin des IDOS, und Dr. Jose Rizal Damuri, Exekutivdirektor des CSIS, die aktuelle globale Krisen sowie mögliche Lehren des „Mandala-Prinzips“ für die Gegenwart beleuchteten. Darüber hinaus übermittelten Mitglieder des MGG-Netzwerks aus Indonesien in einer [Videobotschaft](#) ihre Kriterien für eine erfolgreiche globale Zusammenarbeit. Eva Lynders (Wissenschaftlerin im MGG-Programm, IDOS) moderierte die Sitzung gemeinsam mit Dr. Wulf Reiners (Leiter des MGG-Programms am IDOS).

Die entwickelten Visionen sind so unterschiedlich wie die Hintergründe der Veranstaltungsteilnehmer*innen: Wissenschaftler*innen aus den Bereichen Klimawissenschaften, Digitalisierung und Handel tauschten sich mit Praktiker*innen aus dem Bildungs- und Gesundheitswesen aus. Gemeinsam entwickelten sie Utopien von einer „gleichberechtigten, inklusiven und nachhaltigen globalen Zusammenarbeit durch nahtlose Vernetzung institutioneller Prozesse“, einem „interoperablen System“, „humanitarian by design“ und „aufgeklärten und informierten Gesellschaften“, die auf dem „universellen Zugang zu nahtloser digitaler Konnektivität“, der „Achtung der Rechte von Staaten und Einzelpersonen“ und der Kreislaufwirtschaft basieren. In der zweiten Hälfte der Veranstaltung entwickelten die Teilnehmer*innen Fahrpläne zur Verwirklichung dieser Visionen, indem sie vom Zeitpunkt der Verwirklichung aus rückwärts planten.

Die Veranstaltung bot Raum für Gedankenexperimente und Austausch im Vorfeld des T20-Gipfels. Die Visionen der Teilnehmer*innen für die globale Zusammenarbeit deckten sich sehr gut mit einigen der Politikempfehlungen, die im [T20-Kommuniqué](#) vorgestellt wurden. Eine Reflexion über den Stand der G20 nach dem T20-Gipfel finden Sie [hier](#).

MGG-PRODIGEES Authors Workshop with CIFE: Digitalisation Towards Sustainable Development

By Newsletter | 28. Oktober 2022 | Category: Allgemein

© IDOS

From 21 to 24 September 2022, the [German Institute of Development and Sustainability \(IDOS\)](#) in Bonn, Germany partnered with the [Centre International de Formation Européenne \(CIFE\)](#) to co-host the “MGG-PRODIGEES Authors Workshop with CIFE” in Nice, France. The event brought together 18 experts conspired to form joint publication projects, from blogs to peer-reviewed journal articles, on core topics of digitalisation and sustainable development and featured a series of expert conversations.

As part of the conference, members of the [Cities Coalition for Digital Rights](#), an organisation which works towards legal and ethical frameworks for advancing human rights in digital environments, gave a keynote presentation on the importance of defending digital rights through city action. The city of Bonn joined the CC4DR on September 19, 2022. The workshop also featured a visit to the [Mediterranean Institute of Risk, Environment and Sustainable Development \(IMREDD\)](#) for illustrative discussions on innovation and intelligent technologies for smart city projects. From smart cars to AI in city planning, IMREDD demonstrated how their triad partnership between the public and private sectors and academia is a laboratory for technology that is demoed in cities along the Côte d’Azur.

Four publication projects emerged from the MGG-PRODIGEES Authors Workshop with CIFE: a project on the geopolitics of data governance; one on capacity building on digitalisation for sustainable development; one on the (un)sustainability of digital transformations; and a blog series on digitalisation and inclusion. In 2023, the consortium will reconvene and follow-up on the progress of the PRODIGEES publication projects, at a destination yet to be determined.

PRODIGEES stands for [Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development](#). It is an [EU Horizon 2020](#) funded research staff exchange project from 2020 to 2025, which aims to produce high quality academic publications on the effects of digitalisation as they pertain to governance, society, the economy and the environment. The project is a major instrument of the digitalisation research wing of the [Managing Global Governance \(MGG\)](#) programme at IDOS.

← BACK

08.11.2022

CAN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE COUNTER GROWING INEQUALITY?

Poverty and the widening gap in income and wealth pose an enormous threat to social sustainability and political stability worldwide. During his five months residency in Brazil, Johann Cas (ITA) will explore whether and how artificial intelligence can contribute to sustainable and more equitable development.

There are great hopes and fears associated with the development of AI technologies. One central and still open question is how AI systems can be developed and deployed in an ethical manner.

“So-called ‘artificial intelligence’ is hyped as a key technology for maintaining prosperity and competitiveness. But surprisingly little attention is paid to how AI could actually contribute to an equal distribution of wealth and prosperity” stresses Cas, who works at the Institute of Technology Assessment (ITA) of the Academy of Sciences.

During his five-month research stay at the Fundação Getulio Vargas (FGV) in Rio de Janeiro, he will therefore focus in particular on the question which different concepts of regulating artificial intelligence are suitable for mitigating the problems of increasing inequality at the national and global level. FGV is one of the most influential think tanks both in Latin America and globally.

The exchange will take place within the framework of the PRODIGEES project funded by the EU through the Horizon2020 program. PRODIGEES was funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program H2020-MSCA-RISE-2019 under grant agreement No. [873119].

PRODIGEES project: between a laboratory and a business school in Brazil

By Newsletter | 23. Februar 2023 | Category: Allgemein

Ramona Haegel, Researcher at IDOS and PhD Candidate at the University of Bonn is currently a guest researcher at Escola Brasileira de Administração Pública da Fundação Getulio Vargas (FGV) and at Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro (UERJ) in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil during January and February 2023.

Her research is funded by the [PRODIGEES project](#) (Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe towards Sustainable Development) and the [CSCOPE project](#) funded by BMBF. The EU-funded PRODIGEES project promotes international collaborations and global knowledge sharing on digitalization and sustainability. The CSCOPE project aims to assess the cognitive, technological, social and political processes that play a role in producing scientific marine knowledge in Brazil and Germany.

Ramona's research explores human-techno forces in marine carbon observation systems along the Brazilian coast and the role of digitalization. During her stay, she conducts interviews with scientists at UERJ and FGV, participates in the laboratory work at UERJ to understand human-techno interactions as well as exchanging with FGV colleagues on the science-policy interfaces and inequalities in the Brazilian science system.

*Negotiation processes in the laboratory at UERJ
(Credits: Mirja Schoderer).*

Research Team of IDOS' Postgraduate Programme and FGV colleagues (Credits: FGV).

Digitalization plays a crucial role in marine carbon observations.

Without digital tools, such as two-way communication of autonomous marine carbon observation systems, satellite data as well as digital sharing and accessibility of data, global marine carbon observations and their translation into climate change scenarios would not be possible. Thus, human-techno interactions and forces along these digital observation lines constitute another research unit, which needs an in-depth investigation. Digital technologies and transnational knowledge cooperation enable marine carbon observations as well as climate change predictions and thus need further exploration.

Besides, she also met and exchanged with the Research Team of this year's Postgraduate Programme of IDOS lead by [Sven Grimm](#) and [Wulf Reiners](#). Their [project](#) investigates the understanding of digitalization for sustainability in the Brazilian civil service.

More information about PRODIGEES events, news and publications can be found at www.prodigees.info.

Research team of the Postgraduate Training Programme in Brazil

By Newsletter | 23. Februar 2023 | Category: Allgemein

The team has arrived in Brazil in mid-February and is collecting data for the research, which takes place predominantly in collaboration with the Escola Brasileira de Administração Pública da Fundação Getulio Vargas (FGV EBAPE) and the Escola Nacional de Administração Pública (ENAP).

Their research is partly financed by the [PRODIGEES project](#) (Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe towards Sustainable Development). PRODIGEES, funded by the EU, promotes international collaborations and global knowledge sharing on digitalisation and sustainability in eight countries on five continents, among them Brazil and Germany. Through the exchange of ideas between different academic institutions devoted to sustainability and digitalisation, the project aims to enhance understandings of digital tools and processes and the ways they can be employed to meet the Sustainable Development Goals of the 2030 Agenda.

Digitalisation plays a crucial role in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. To steer processes in favour of sustainable digitalisation, knowledge of digitalisation and sustainability, as well as an overview of the opportunities and risks of their interconnection, is of great importance for policy-makers and the civil sector in general. In this regard, civil servants hold a highly relevant position, being involved in both the formulation and implementation of policies and thus displaying considerable potential to steer digitalisation towards higher levels of sustainability in Brazil.

The team's research explores the understanding of digitalisation for sustainability in the civil service of Brazil. To obtain in-depth insights into the issue, the team applies a mix of both quantitative and qualitative methods – on the one hand, by sending out a survey to civil servants in Brazil and, on the other hand, by conducting semi-structured interviews throughout different research sites in the country. The latter refer to both municipalities, such as Rio de Janeiro, Recife and Curitiba as well as to the federal level in Brasília. Through the choice of different administrative and regional levels, the team expects to develop a broad understanding of the current topics within digitalisation in Brazil and how these are linked to sustainability, especially the ecological dimension thereof.

Research Team of IDOS' Postgraduate Programme and FGV colleagues (Credits: FGV).

Research team III of 58th Postgraduate Training Programme enters their last phase of research in Brazil

By Newsletter | 28. März 2023 | Category: Allgemein

The research team on Sustainable Digitalisation in Brazil's civil service, has just finished its data collection phase. The group is now about to start analysing the information obtained in different research sites throughout the country in the past five weeks.

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The team had started its research trip in Rio de Janeiro in February, where the Escola Brasileira de Administração Pública da Fundação Getulio Vargas (FGV EBAPE), one of the two project partner institutions, is based. For first local insights into digitalisation and how it is linked to sustainability, the team met with different experts and advisors to discuss current trends and endeavors in both fields. While doing so, it stayed in close exchange with FGV EBAPE to ensure the relevance and proper embeddedness of the research in the local context.

The team then travelled to the capital Brasília to explore the research topic at the federal level in more depth. Assuming that civil servants hold a highly relevant position with regards to steering political processes in favour of sustainable digitalisation, it predominantly focused on representatives of different federal institutions based in Brasília to conduct semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, and a participatory workshop. Interviews were conducted with representatives of the Ministry of Management and Innovation in Public Services, the Ministry of the Environment, the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Labour. Further, state bodies and companies devoted to both environmental and digital matters were also interviewed. During this research phase, the close cooperation with the Escola Nacional de Administração Pública (ENAP), the second partner institution, based in Brasília, facilitated not only the exchange of relevant information but also the establishment of contacts for interviews. Through this, the research team was able to gain a comprehensive overview of the different perspectives of and experiences with sustainable digitalisation at the federal level in Brazil.

For the concluding data collection period, the team split up into two groups, with one sub-team travelling to Curitiba and the other travelling to Recife to further explore sustainable digitalisation at the municipal level in different socio-economic setups. Talking not only to municipal governments and city halls but also to enterprises devoted to technology and digitalisation, both sub-teams obtained further insights to complement the research findings made at the federal level.

Now, the team has reunited to enter the last phase of the fieldwork period in Brazil: data analysis. During a three-week retreat in Paraty, it will transcribe, code, and discuss the data collected on site in Brazil. To facilitate this process, a two-day workshop with key contributors to the research will be held at the beginning of April. By presenting and discussing preliminary results, it aims to receive the feedback of an external sounding board to guide not only the final presentation in Rio de Janeiro, planned for April 13, but also the finalisation of the study back in Bonn.

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Research stay in Jakarta: IDOS researcher Benjamin Stewart looks at Open Science in relation to science policy

By Newsletter | 28. März 2023 | Category: Allgemein

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From January to March 2023, the [Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development](#) (PRODIGEES) project facilitated a research exchange of IDOS research staff member Benjamin Stewart in Jakarta, Indonesia.

MGG Network partner, the Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) in Jakarta, hosted Mr Stewart during his investigation of Open Science and science policy implementation in Indonesia and the Asia Pacific Region. Mr Stewart conducted qualitative research, interviewing directors at the Indonesian National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), as well as professors, directors, and staff of Indonesian universities, research institutes and civil society organisations. The research comes at a pivotal moment, with Indonesia taking on the ASEAN presidency in 2023 and potentially asserting itself as a regional science and technology power player. There is potential for science and technology policy development that could inspire [similar action within the G20](#).

The PRODIGEES exchange also connected Mr Stewart to MGG Network partner, the Indonesian National Institute of Public Administration (LAN). With LAN, Mr Stewart presented IDOS' MGG Academy programming, linking the work of the Academy with trainings that LAN hosts for civil servants. Further, with the Jakarta Polytechnic STIA LAN division, Mr Stewart presented on the topic of Global Citizenship Education, which presented IDOS and MGG visions of inter- and transnational network cooperation and global common good.

Both CSIS and LAN are progenitors of MGG Academy alumni, and longstanding partners of the MGG Network.

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The research of Mr Stewart conducted under the PRODIGEES aegis contributes to both his PhD work, supervised by Director Prof. Dr Anna-Katharina Hornidge with the University of Bonn, and to the PRODIGEES work package on research related to "governance and society". PRODIGEES is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska Curie Action – Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (MSCA-RISE), to be carried about between January 2020 and June 2025. Mr Stewart is the manager of this project.

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Postgraduate Training Programme: Brazil Research Team evaluates data in Bonn

By Newsletter | 25. April 2023 | Category: Allgemein

The research team of the 58th postgraduate class, which is conducting research on digitisation for sustainability in the public sector in Brazil, returned from their nine-week research stay in Brazil.

© IDOS, Research Team 3 with participants of the workshop in Paraty

It is the first of the three research teams, which returned and will further analyse the data to complete the final report. After the six-week data collection phase in Brazil, which the team conducted in the cities of Rio de Janeiro, Brasília, Curitiba and Recife, a three-week team retreat took place in Paraty, federal state of Rio de Janeiro. There, the research team began with the analysis of the collected data. Based on this preliminary analysis, the team established initial theses and discussed them in a two-day workshop with a focus group consisting of the two partner institutions of the research project (FGV EBAPE and ENAP) and relevant ministries. The interactive design of the workshop allowed the participants to bring their different experiences, perspectives and competences into the discussion, which led to the preliminary results being even better contextualised in the Brazilian regional context.

Before leaving for Germany, the research team returned to Rio de Janeiro for a few days to present its preliminary research results at the partner organisation FGV EBAPE. Project and interview partners from other parts of the country participated online and discussed the first impressions and results.

Back in Germany, the evaluation of further data, the completion of the final report and the final presentation at IDOS will follow at the end of May.

[Building Climate Resilience in Urban Informal Settlements through Data Co-production](#)

Giulia Sofia Sarno

Climate change is worsening the number, frequency and duration of natural hazards across the globe, and urban informal settlements are among the most vulnerable areas. These neighbourhoods are built within the ‘formal’ city but outside of the official system of laws and regulations aimed at ensuring safe settlements, exposing therefore communities to increased risks, including those of extreme events caused by climate change. In these contexts, localised resilience practices that address the differential socio-spatially determined vulnerability to natural hazards through the active engagement of communities can be very effective approaches. In particular, data co-production practices can address the widespread issue of data gaps in informal settlements, allowing for a correct assessment of risks, vulnerabilities and resilience capacity in these communities. Implementation of data co-production practices in Brazilian favelas affected by floods is providing important evidence about their potential to reduce deaths and damages while also increasing climate change awareness and digital literacy.

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PRODIGEES research exchanges at IDOS

By Newsletter | 28. Juni 2023 | Category: Allgemein

From May to July 2023, IDOS hosts fellows from the Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) in Indonesia and Fundação Getúlio Vargas (FGV) in Brazil within the PRODIGEE project.

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The research exchanges are facilitated by the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation staff exchange project, Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development (PRODIGEES). The project is coordinated by IDOS and brings together network partners from Brazil, India, Indonesia, Mexico, South Africa and the EU.

PRODIGEES fellow Dr Medelina Hendyito, who is Deputy Director of CSIS, researches how think tanks engage with digital platforms, on the research level as well as on communications and network level. The study is a comparison between contexts in Germany and Indonesia.

A few doors down the hall, PRODIGEES fellow Prof. Juliana Mansur from FGV researches how (and if) digital technologies empower female entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector. Juliana Mansur also makes a comparative study between Brazil and Germany.

In parallel, PRODIGEES facilitates more research exchanges between network partners during the summer period, including from South Africa and Indonesia to EU-based PRODIGEES partners.

Recent meetings with the PRODIGEES External Scientific Advisory Board and with the project's European Research Executive Agency (REA) Project Officer affirmed PRODIGEES' successful implementation despite Covid-19 related difficulties in the first two years. The project implementation greatly benefits from the extraordinary interest in network cooperation, long-term knowledge cooperation and the topicality of the research topic, ie. digitalisation for sustainability.

For a full list of PRODIGEES news, events, and publications, please visit the project website at www.prodigees.info. All PRODIGEES publications, presentations, and digital knowledge products are available open access in the [PRODIGEES Research Community](#) on Zenodo.

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T20 Side Event “Utopias for Global Cooperation: Toward joint visions for Global Digital Commons”

By Newsletter | 21. August 2023 | Category: Allgemein

Es ist nicht alltäglich für Forschende der führenden Think Tanks der „Group of 20“ (G20) Staaten, Utopien zu entwerfen. Während eines Side Events im Rahmen des Gipfels der [Think 20 \(T20\) Engagement Group](#), der vom 31. Juli bis 02. August im Kontext der indischen G20 Präsidentschaft in Mysuru, Indien, stattfand, haben Forschende und Praktiker*innen genau das getan. Unter dem Titel “Utopias for Global Cooperation: Toward joint visions for Global Digital Commons”, organisiert von [Gateway House](#), [Indian Council on Global Relations](#) und dem Managing Global Governance (MGG) Programme des IDOS, erarbeiteten die Teilnehmenden in Gruppen Bausteine für ein gemeinsames Verständnis von Globalen Digitalen Gemeingütern. Die Veranstaltung war Teil eines Forschungsaufenthaltes im Rahmen des [Projekts „Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development“ \(PRODIGEES\)](#).

Participants of the Side Events together organisers from Gateway House (Manjeet Kripalani, Executive Director and Aliasger Bootwalla, Manager Media and Outreach) and IDOS (Dr. Wulf Reiners, Head of MGG Programme, Vy Dang, Researcher and Eva Lynders, Researcher). ©IDOS

Prof. Dr. Anna-Katharina Hornidge (Director of IDOS), Mr. Sharad Sharma (Governing Council & Co-Founder of iSPIRT (Indian Software Product Industry RoundTable)) and Prof. Dr. Denis Snower (President of the Global Solutions Initiative) ©IDOS

Organisers of the Side Event (left to right): Dr. Wulf Reiners (Head of MGG Programme), Eva Lynders (Researcher in MGG Programme), Aliasger Bootwalla (Manager Media and Outreach, Gateway House), Vy Dang (Researcher in MGG Programme), Manjeet Kripalani (Executive Director, Gateway House), ©IDOS

Group work for the development of “utopias” on Global Digital Commons, ©IDOS

Geleitet durch die Idee von „Utopien“ zielte das interaktive Veranstaltungsformat drauf ab, unterschiedliche Perspektiven und Zielvorstellungen in der gemeinschaftlichen Formulierung von Vision für Global Digital Commons zusammenzubringen. In einem so genannten Back-Casting-Prozess skizzierten fünf Arbeitsgruppen zentrale Schritte zur Umsetzung positiver Zukunftsvisionen, die in der gegenwärtigen G20 Präsidentschaft ihren Ausgang nehmen könnten.

Kurzvorträge von Prof. Dr. Anna-Katharina Hornidge (Direktorin des IDOS), Herrn Sharad Sharma (Governing Council & Co-Founder von iSPIRT (Indian Software Product Industry RoundTable)) und Prof. Dr. Denis Snower (President der Global Solutions Initiative) adressierten Kernelemente und Beispiele Digitaler Gemeingüter: Wissens- und Forschungssysteme, öffentliche digitale Infrastruktur („Digital Public Infrastructure“, DPI) und die Sicherheit persönlicher Daten.

Die Frage, wie die G20 Staaten zu einem gemeinsamen, globalen Verständnis und gemeinsamen Rahmenbedingungen für globale digitale Gemeingüter beitragen können, war auch Kernfrage der [Task Force 2 \(„Our Common Digital Future“\)](#) des diesjährigen T20 Prozesses. Darüber hinaus ist das Konzept zentral für die geplante Ausarbeitung des [Global Digital Compact](#) der Vereinten Nationen. Als einziges interaktives und Task Force-übergreifendes Format zu Globalen Digitalen Gemeingütern im Rahmen des diesjährigen T20 Gipfels hat die Veranstaltung einen wichtigen Raum für den transnationalen Austausch und die Vernetzung von Expertinnen und Experten geboten.

PRODIGEES: IDOS-Expertinnen führen Interviews im Amazonas

By Newsletter | 26. Oktober 2023 | Category: Allgemein

IDOS-Wissenschaftlerin und Doktorandin [Ramona Haegele](#) sowie Kommunikationsreferentin [Sabrina Heuwinkel](#) haben zehn Tage an der von [FGV EBAPE](#) organisierten Amazonas-Expedition teil genommen.

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FGV EBAPE bietet mit der „Amazonas immersion experience“ brasilianischen und internationalen Studierenden einen Kurs im Master in Management (MIM) mit einem besonderen Fokus auf Nachhaltigkeit. Der Aufenthalt von Ramona Hägele und Sabrina Heuwinkel bei FGV EBAPE in Rio de Janeiro sowie an der Expedition im Amazonas erfolgte über [PRODIGEES](#), einem von der Europäischen Union geförderten Forschungsprojekt, welches den Themenkomplex von Digitalisierung, Umwelt, Wirtschaft, Regierung und Gesellschaft bearbeitet.

Während der Expedition konnten die Studierenden aus erster Hand Umweltprojekte und nachhaltige Managementpraktiken kennenlernen, die von verschiedenen Akteur*innen des öffentlichen und privaten Sektors im Amazonasgebiet durchgeführt werden. Während des Programms lernten die Teilnehmer*innen, wie z.B. Kleinproduzent*innen und Kooperativen zusammenarbeiten und Unternehmertum, Digitalisierung und Nachhaltigkeit erfolgreich miteinander verbinden.

Durch die Teilnahme der IDOS-Expertinnen erhielten die Studierenden zudem Einblicke in die Anwendung qualitativer Forschungsmethoden, in die professionelle Videoproduktion und in die Wissenschaftskommunikation. Zudem wurden sie bei der Erstellung ihrer schriftlichen und visuellen Projektarbeit über die Expedition unterstützt.

Die Video-Dokumentations-Clips, die die besuchten Projekte und Initiativen im Amazonas vorstellen, werden über IDOS auf [X](#) und [LinkedIn](#) veröffentlicht.

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Trailer | Synergetic Stories on Sustainability and Digitalisation | PRODIGEES

PRODIGEES

Synergetic stories in Brazil

Feldforschung vom Amazonas bis zur brasilianischen Küste

By Newsletter | 28. Februar 2024 | Category: Allgemein

Umweltprojekte aus erster Hand und nachhaltige Managementpraktiken in der Amazonasregion: Ramona Haegele (IDOS) produzierte gemeinsam mit Sabrina Heuwinkel (IDOS) eine Videoserie über Projekte, die Unternehmertum, Digitalisierung und Nachhaltigkeit miteinander vereinen.

Von links: Andrew Deneault (IDOS), Roberto Pimenta (FGV EBAPE), Juliana Mansur (FGV EBAPE) und Ramona Haegele (IDOS) bei FGV EBAPE in Brasilien., ©IDOS

Ramona Haegele, Forscherin und Doktorandin am IDOS, war von September 2023 bis Januar 2024 als Gastwissenschaftlerin bei **FGV EBAPE**, Rio de Janeiro, Brasilien tätig. Im Rahmen des EU-geförderten Projekts **PRODIGEES**, das sich mit der Schnittstelle von Nachhaltigkeit, Digitalisierung und transnationaler Wissenskooperation beschäftigt, konnte die IDOS-Forscherin in Brasilien ihre Feldforschung durchführen.

Im Oktober nahm die Forscherin an einem 10-tägigen Programm des Sustainability Tracks des Masters in Management (MIM) der FGV EBAPE im brasilianischen Amazonasgebiet teil. Während des Programms beobachteten die Studierenden der FGV EBAPE sowie die Forscher*innen aus erster Hand Umweltprojekte und nachhaltige Managementpraktiken, die von Akteur*innen aus dem öffentlichen und privaten Sektor in der Amazonasregion durchgeführt werden. Dabei lernten die Teilnehmenden, wie z.B. Kleinproduzent*innen und Kooperativen zusammenarbeiten und Unternehmertum, Digitalisierung und Nachhaltigkeit erfolgreich miteinander verbinden. Gemeinsam mit **Sabrina Heuwinkel**, Kommunikationsreferentin am IDOS, produzierten sie eine **Videoserie**, die die Projekte vorstellt.

Neben der Vermittlung von qualitativen Forschungsmethoden an die MIM-Studierenden und der Einbindung in die Arbeit der FGV EBAPE in Rio de Janeiro,

führte Ramona Haegele Interviews mit Vertreter*innen der **Liga das Mulheres Pelos Oceanos**, einem Netzwerk von Frauen, die zum Schutz der Ozeane arbeiten. Durch die Interviews gewann sie Einblicke in die (Un-)Gleichstellung und Diskriminierung von Frauen und Minderheiten in den Meereswissenschaften. Diese Erkenntnisse werden ihre Daten über die Wissensproduktionsprozesse bei der marinen Kohlenstoffbeobachtung in Deutschland und Brasilien ergänzen, was auch ihr Promotionsprojekt darstellt.

Sabrina Heuwinkel (IDOS), Juliana Mansur (FGV EBAPE) und Ramona Haegele (IDOS) bei FGV EBAPE in Rio de Janeiro.

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Constructive communication in the fake news era

An EU-backed project explains how applying the principles of constructive journalism can help us communicate evidence-based knowledge more effectively.

DIGITAL ECONOMY SOCIETY

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What can science communication learn from constructive journalism in a world bombarded with fake news? Sabrina Heuwinkel and Ramona Hägele from the German Institute of Development and Sustainability lay down some guidelines in the [27 March 2024 edition](#) of 'The Current Column', a publication tackling key issues and trends in international development policy.

The article was published as part of the EU-funded [PRODIGEES](#) project that is studying the effects of digitalisation on the environment, economy, governance and society. PRODIGEES brings together partners from eight countries across the globe – Austria, Brazil, Germany, India, Indonesia, Italy, Mexico and South Africa – to explore digitalisation's social, governmental, economic and climatic impacts from local, regional, national and global perspectives.

Emphasising the perils faced by a digitalised society undergoing numerous crises at once, Heuwinkel and Hägele write: "Fake news spreads across the globe in seconds and can cost lives. Disinformation weakens democracy and social cohesion. Against this backdrop, evidence-based knowledge urgently needs to be communicated more effectively."

With the important role that science communication has to play in this context, constructive journalism can provide considerable impetus. But what precisely is constructive journalism? According to the authors, it encompasses "a pronounced focus on solutions; multiple perspectives ...; and a constructive dialogue," not only focusing on describing a problem but also looking at what happens next.

Pitting science against fake news

The authors mention including constructive approaches from the start when designing science communication. They also highlight the importance of using more resources, such as podcasts, infographics, animations and explainer videos. "This is the only way to ensure that evidence-based scientific content stands a chance in the ruthless competition for attention on social media platforms," they write. "AI-based tools will provide important support here."

Related projects

HORIZON 2020

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Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe towards Sustainable Development

PRODIGEES

22 April 2025

MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs at Stellenbosch University

By Newsletter | 29. Mai 2024 | Category: Allgemein

In the labs, four groups worked on governance, society, environment and economy. The outcomes are planned to contribute to international efforts to harness digital technologies for sustainable development in the T20 process and beyond.

MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs in Stellenbosch, ©IDOS

From 28 April to 3 May 2024, the MGG-PRODIGEES Policy Labs were held in Stellenbosch and Cape Town, South Africa, marking a milestone in the network's cooperation on digitalisation research for public policy. The event was orchestrated under the joint auspices of IDOS' [Managing Global Governance \(MGG\) Network](#) and the European Union's Horizon 2020 funded [PRODIGEES project](#), in collaboration with Stellenbosch University.

The week-long series of Labs engaged 21 researchers and experts from 14 institutions and 8 countries in a focussed, collaborative effort to craft policy briefs addressing the dual themes of digitalisation and sustainable development. The sessions, held at the Stellenbosch Institute for Advanced Study (STIAS), were designed to foster the development of actionable policy recommendations based on the PRODIGEES secondments undertaken in the last years. The Labs established four dedicated groups, each focussed on one of the project's thematic intersections with digitalisation: governance, society, environment and economy.

The labs also included a symposium by Professor Willem Fourie, founder of the [Innovation Policy Lab](#) at Stellenbosch University. In an exchange with him and further representatives of Stellenbosch University, the group examined political narratives in South Africa in times of elections, among other things. The lab concluded with a visit to Code for Africa in Cape Town, where the role of data collection and analysis for journalism on the African continent was highlighted. This excursion thus provided a practical illustration of how digital tools and data-driven approaches can impact sustainable development practices.

The Policy Labs were organised back-to-back with the [IDOS/NSG-MGG Conference "International Capacity Development for the Civil Service – The Sustainable Digitalisation Agenda"](#) in Cape Town, South Africa, from May 5 to 8, 2024. Both initiatives were implemented in connection with the secondments of IDOS researchers Dr Sven Grimm, Matthias Kachelmann, Dr Wulf Reiners and Benjamin Stewart to Stellenbosch University in the framework of the PRODIGEES staff exchange scheme.

Joint Conference of the National School of Government of South Africa and MGG

By Newsletter | 29. Mai 2024 | Category: Allgemein

During the event „International Capacity Development for the Civil Service – The Sustainable Digitalisation Agenda“, IDOS and the National School of Government of South Africa (NSG) underscored their commitment to ongoing collaboration by signing a joint cooperation framework.

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From 5-8 May, the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) and the National School of Government of South Africa (NSG) hosted a three-day conference on "International Capacity Development for the Civil Service – The Sustainable Digitalisation Agenda" in Cape Town, South Africa. It brought together more than 60 international representatives of national schools of public administration and other training institutions to exchange on the potentials and challenges in leveraging digitalisation towards sustainable development, and the implications for the training of civil servants.

The National School of Government of South Africa (NSG) and the Managing Global Governance (MGG) programme implemented by IDOS [have been engaging with the MGG network in public sector capacity development](#) for the implementation of the United Nation's Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development since early 2018. During the event, IDOS and the NSG underlined their commitment to ongoing collaboration by signing a [Memorandum of Understanding \(MoU\)](#).

The joint conference provided opportunities for competence development through international knowledge-sharing and a series of hands-on workshops, for instance on the social impact of Artificial Intelligence. Additionally, the event facilitated peer-exchange and network-building to advance the collaboration agenda for 2025 and 2026. Following the opening remarks from representatives of the hosting institutions and the German Embassy, Pretoria, highlights entailed a hybrid session of the NSG Master Class Series on "Artificial Intelligence as a Tool for the Achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)" by the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR, South Africa), a roundtable discussion between national schools of public administrations from Brazil, India, Indonesia, and South Africa, and a panel discussion with digitalisation experts from South Africa and Germany.

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The Conference was organised by IDOS and the NSG in connection to the [MGG/PRODIGEES Policy Labs](#) on digitalisation towards sustainable development (Stellenbosch, April 28 – May 3), and in affiliation to the [PRODIGEES](#) project of the Managing Global Governance (MGG) programme with financial support from the Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ), the Ministry of Culture and Science of the German State of North Rhine-Westphalia (MKW), and co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

The Geopolitics of Digitalization

Prof Janis van der Westhuizen | Stellenbosch University

BRAZIL, SOUTH AFRICA & THE BAN ON HUAWEI

Although the invasion of Ukraine in 2022 is widely seen as the *Zeitenwende* of a multipolar order, the earlier attempts by the United States to restrict the adoption of Huawei's 5G information and communications technology (ICT) systems worldwide already revealed the growing salience of geopolitical tensions.

Concerns over digital privacy and outright accusations of spying between Washington and Beijing eventually culminated in May 2019 by the US initiating a (relatively) successful campaign of convincing its allies in Asia not to adopt Huawei's 5G systems or, at least, impose operating conditions that would also heavily restrict its adoption amongst members of the EU.

In much of the Global South, however, Washington faced an uphill battle to extend the ban on Huawei ICT systems. In most of the developing world an obvious explanation was a simple cost/benefit calculation. By the 2020s, Huawei – which had focused on expanding its market share in Latin America and Africa since the mid-1990s – had become too established, as well as much more affordable than Ericsson or Nokia, for both ICT service providers and governments in the developing world to uphold the ban.

The move was also a non-starter politically. For many governments in the developing world China has not only become one of their most important trading partners, but also an alternative source of development financing. The Huawei dispute revealed the new challenge facing the Global South in the 2020s of how to navigate the growing tensions between the US and China amidst a polarizing global order in which states are expected to choose sides.

The Huawei dispute also forced Brazil and South Africa into a corner. However, despite their broad similarities as highly unequal, 'semi-peripheral' regional powers, the two countries responded very differently.

Given the Bolsonaro government's desire to ideologically align itself firmly with President Trump, Brasilia was particularly receptive to Washington's demands. These were amplified by

Trump indicating that the US would scale down intelligence and other forms of cooperation if Brazil failed to thwart Huawei's growing 5G presence. Concurrently, some of Bolsonaro's cabinet ministers (most notably, the foreign minister Ernesto Araujo) and Eduardo Bolsonaro (the president's son) repeatedly published openly anti-Chinese comments, souring diplomatic relations between Brazil and China, even though China had become Brazil's most important trading partner.

However, the tensions between Brazil's pro-US political signalling and its de facto economic relationship with Beijing resonated in very different ways across Bolsonaro's varied support coalitions. The most decisive in this regard was the powerful agribusiness lobby which feared that the growing tensions with Beijing were jeopardizing exports. These conditions meant that in Brazil, the Huawei dispute reflected the ideologically polarized foreign policy debates of the Bolsonaro era.

In South Africa, by contrast, the Huawei dispute became largely 'de-politicized'. President Ramaphosa famously contended that the US was simply 'jealous' of Huawei's success and that the country's economy risked being held hostage to the trade war between China and the US. Unlike the Bolsonarista narratives about support for the US affirming Brazil's 'Western' identity, the South African narratives tended to be more 'technical' and highlighted Huawei's potential for economic development.

Attempts by the US to portray the

Global South's reluctance to adopt a ban against Huawei as a security threat were severely undermined in both Brazil and South Africa by the issue of vaccine access amidst the Covid-19 pandemic. This was not only because Covid constituted a far more immediate and profound threat than the adoption of a Chinese-developed ICT system, but also because of the West's initial reluctance to support an intellectual property patent waiver which would enable generic sources to be developed in the developing world.

Whereas non-Western powers used 'vaccine diplomacy' to generate soft power, Western responses appeared to perpetuate global inequity. For example, many South Africans interpreted as punishment the unprecedented and unexpected travel bans imposed on the country by the UK, the US and others in Europe in November 2021, following South African epidemiologists' discovery of the Omicron variant given that no similar measures were imposed on other countries where Omicron was discovered at the same time.

In Brazil, Bolsonaro's unorthodox response to the pandemic and the initial denial of the severity of Covid caused amongst the highest fatalities in the Global South, severely threatening the legitimacy of the far-right government. In desperation, Bolsonaro's minister of telecommunications (possibly due to constant policy differences between the President and the Health Ministry) sought assistance from various telecom firms (including Ericsson and Nokia) to acquire vaccines in February 2021. Huawei indicated that the Brazilian

request would be relayed to the Chinese government. By late February, the first doses of Chinese vaccines were being administered in Brazil and two weeks later, the Brazilian government announced that Huawei would not be excluded from the country's 5G auction.

Three conditions explain why Washington's attempts to prohibit the rollout of Huawei's 5G systems in Brazil and South Africa have failed.

First, bad timing. Not only was the Covid crisis a far more immediate and profound threat than Huawei, but ambivalent Western responses prompted many to question Western reliability.

Second, the sheer cost of removing and then blocking Huawei, a well-established player in both countries, simply overrode the very limited and unclear benefits of doing so (not to

mention opposition from Brazilian and South African telecom firms).

Third, militating against retaliatory action against Huawei was the sheer fact that China had become both Pretoria's and Brasilia's most important trading partner. Within Bolsonaro's cabinet, minister's sensitive to Brazil's anti-Chinese orientation, especially in trade and agriculture, eventually tilted the balance of power against any Huawei 5G ban.

This text is an abbreviated version of a forthcoming article in Revista Brasileira de Política Internacional 67 (2), 2024 funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme 'PRODIGEES - Promoting Research on Digitalization in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development' (2020-2025) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 873119.

Windows of Opportunity

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IAI
notes on...

No.08 - September 2024

South Africa's G20 Presidency

In 2025, South Africa will become the first African country to assume the G20 presidency – taking over from Brazil. Representing 85 per cent of the global economy, 75 per cent of global trade, and 63 per cent of the world's population, the G20 plays a pivotal role in shaping global governance. Policies adopted by its members have far-reaching implications, making it a crucial platform for driving global transformative change. South Africa should prioritise three key areas: reforming the global financial architecture, addressing climate change through a just energy transition, and transforming food systems. Focusing on these issues will create a solid foundation for Africa's economic leapfrogging and sustainable development.

 [Darlington Tshuma](#)
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The EU and Forest Protection

The EU Regulation on Deforestation (EUDR) is the first ever to directly address the main cause of global deforestation: agriculture. The regulation prohibits the export to the EU market of agricultural commodities whose production has caused deforestation as of 31 December 2020. The path to EUDR approval sparked significant protests, initially from major partner countries such as Indonesia and Brazil and later, in 2023, from a broader segment of the Global South. By 2024, even some EU member states, along with the United States and Australia, voiced objections. The opposition has been so substantial that, despite the regulation being in effect for over a year, its future remains uncertain, and there is increasing potential for its implementation to be delayed by one or two years.

 [Lorenzo Colantoni](#)
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INTERNATIONAL FUTURES (IF) programme: Insights into Sustainable Digitalisation

By Newsletter | 24. Oktober 2024 | Category: Allgemein

The ten-day programme of IF serves to build networks between decision-makers from diplomacy, science, politics, civil society, and business. As 21st edition, the INTERNATIONAL FUTURES (IF) programme took place from 9 to 18 October 2024 in Berlin.

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With a focus on "Sustainable Digitalisation", IF brought together participants of the [Managing Global Governance \(MGG\) Academy](#) with young diplomats as part of the Federal Foreign Office's International Training for Diplomats (Diplomacy by Networking). As a dialogue format at the interface of diplomacy, sustainable development and digitalisation, it is also linked to the work of the [PRODIGEES project](#), which has been implemented in the [MGG network](#) since 2020.

In expert discussions, interactive workshops and simulation games, the group explored the opportunities and risks of artificial intelligence, the influence of social media, big data and digital platforms. Another focus was on the challenges of inclusive digitalisation and the digital agenda for global governance. In this context, the group met with Gesa Bräutigam, Special Envoy for Feminist Foreign Policy and Director for Human Rights and Global Health. Another highlight was the meeting with Niels Annen, Parliamentary State Secretary to the Minister for Economic Cooperation and Development, to discuss the link between sustainable development and diplomacy, and the cooperation agendas between Germany and the countries represented. The programme also included a cultural excursion in Berlin, including a political city tour and visits to the Humboldt Forum and the East Side Gallery.

Technology as a Catalyst Driving the Youth Engagement in Global Development – Boon or a Bane?

By Blog | 12. November 2024 | Category: Allgemein, Future of Globalisation |

Photo by Keira Burton: <https://www.pexels.com/photo/multiracial-positive-male-and-female-students-using-smartphones-in-city-park-6146931/>

Digital development has tremendously transformed lives and interactions across the globe during the past decades. The [2023 International Telecommunication Union \(ITU\)](#) statistic shows, almost four in five (79%) of world's youth aged between 15 and 24 use the internet, making the youth a generation of digital natives. Overall, more than two-thirds (67%) of the world's population are internet users.

Digital technology creates opportunities and possibilities for youth to access education, training and employment, enhancing their possibilities to break intergenerational poverty circle, creating a more mobilised and innovative world. The abundant resources and knowledge that youth can access through digital platforms could also empower them for their self-development.

Youth and Digital Divide

While young people in high-income countries are driving forward the digital transformation, young people in the lower income countries are still struggling with the digital infrastructure affordability and internet accessibility challenges. According to the [2023 ITU](#) statistics regarding the percentages of youth internet users, there is a two times gap between the high income countries (98%) and the lower income countries (45%); African countries are the most affected, remaining 53% in comparison to 98% in European countries.

Digital divide does not only exist between countries in different income groups, but also persists as a significant gap within and among different nations, regions (rural and urban), genders, age groups, etc. This disparity is evident in varying levels of digital literacy and skills among youth, which, despite theoretically global access to information, de facto results in unequal opportunities in the labour market.

The intersection of youth and technology presents a complex paradigm – while digital platforms enable unprecedented opportunities for social, economic, and political engagement, they simultaneously expose young people to significant risks, particularly in the realms of privacy, data security, and digital violence. According to the [2021 UNDP](#) regional survey, young activists expressed that fake news (85%) and extremists' content online (73%) are the top two challenges.

Data Security and Digital Violence

As young users increasingly engage with online platforms, their personal information is frequently harvested by tech companies for data-driven business models, often without informed consent or a full understanding of the risks. This raises critical concerns about data commodification and privacy awareness, particularly for young users who may lack digital literacy. However, large tech corporations earn profit from youth-generated content and personal data, offering little in return for the exploitation of their digital footprints. For example, the 2019 Facebook data breach, which exposed the personal information of over 500 million users, serves as a stark reminder of the data vulnerability that accompanies digital participation for all including youth.

The problem is further compounded by the prevalence of digital violence, a term that encompasses cyberbullying, online harassment, and hate speech – phenomena that disproportionately affect women, minorities, and other marginalised communities. Recent studies highlight that nearly [60% of U.S. teenagers have experienced some forms of cyberbullying](#), which can severely impact mental health, leading to more anxiety, depression, and in extreme cases, self-harm. Youth from disadvantaged backgrounds are particularly susceptible, facing compounded risks in both the virtual and physical worlds.

As cybercrime evolves, the impact on youth is becoming increasingly pronounced. For example, [The TalkTalk Hack \(BBC, 2018\)](#) – the company incurred millions of pounds in fines and reparations due to a security breach caused by a 15 years old boy who used simple techniques to gain unauthorised access to personal details of thousands of customers. Such incidents highlight not only the vulnerability of digital infrastructures but also the pressing need for governments and tech companies to adopt proactive cybersecurity protocols that can protect and prevent the youth from cybercrime.

In light of these issues, it becomes imperative for stakeholders – ranging from policymakers to tech companies – to practice a clear approach to digital ethics, emphasising individual choice and youth protections for young users. By fostering digital literacy and creating robust safety frameworks, we can mitigate the darker aspects of youth's digital engagement and ensure that technology remains a force for empowerment rather than exploitation.

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← BACK 10.12.2024

INTERVIEW: IN A DIGITALIZED WORLD, WHO HAS THE RIGHT TO THE CITY?

Facial recognition, smart lampposts, and sensors throughout the city capture information - how do governments use big data and artificial intelligence (AI) to make decisions that impact collective rights? How does this affect people living in cities?

For two months, ITA researcher Rafaela Cavalcanti de Alcantara visited Instituto Mora in Mexico City to find out more about how digitization affects people living in cities in different ways, when aspects like gender, sexual orientation, ability, ethnicity, and class, for instance, are taken into consideration.

Rafaela Cavalcanti de Alcantara, you spent two months in Mexico during the EU PRODIGEES project researching the impact of digitization on urban planning and human rights. What were the experiences that will stay with you the most?

Cavalcanti de Alcantara: As a Latin American researcher in diaspora, it is meaningful when I have the opportunity for an exchange with colleagues about issues relevant for Latin America. Being hosted by Instituto Mora fostered significant encounters with researchers and students who also have been elaborating on themes like territorialities, social struggles, and new technologies. Moreover, my exchange with the Center for Gender Researches and Studies of the National Autonomous University of Mexico was a highlight of my stay. I attended three workshops they offered, visited their Fanzine library, and had relevant talks with their staff and researchers connected to the centre. It was exceptional to get to know their transdisciplinarity as well as experience generosity as an academic practice both at Instituto Mora and CIEG.

What led you to do research about "body-territory"? Can you explain the concept?

Cavalcanti de Alcantara: The concept of body-territory itself comes originally from Latin America. It raises awareness about how the exploitation of common goods, such as indigenous, urban or rural land, involves the violation of the body of each person as well as the collective body. Coming from Brazil and being currently based in Europe makes me think about a colonialist past and present, so questions of territory, of what land who is entitled to use and why, are always crucial. Also, I think about the body as the first place we occupy in the world. What those bodies represent affects the access to, or exclusion from, specific spaces and rights.

This research trip gave me an opportunity to look at the increasing use of databases to manage cities. I also got to further explore the body-territory concept. By raising awareness about the situation of each body in the world, it challenges the liberal idea of the "individual" as being a cis-white male. I believe this is important because "abstract" or "imagined" urban citizen models consider rights somehow "taken for granted." However, when thinking about people living in the cities, we should consider conditions in the real world.

You are focusing on the digitization of cities in your research. How is that related to technology assessment?

Cavalcanti de Alcantara: Digitization or datafication of cities may refer to a diversity of initiatives deployed in urban spaces, often including new technologies involving big data. Bearing in mind those contexts, for technology assessment we should consider that there is no such thing as a neutral technological tool or neutral knowledge production. Ideas, priorities, budget allocation, urban policies, and data analysis come from situated perspectives and views about the world. Therefore, assuming the lack of neutrality in technology is an essential initial step to avoid thinking about "one size fits all" urban technological tools.

PRODIGEES 2024: Bridging Digitalisation and Sustainability Through Research and Innovation Staff Exchanges

By Newsletter | 16. Dezember 2024 | Category: Allgemein

In 2024, the EU Horizon 2020 funded **PRODIGEES** project showcased the impact of international collaboration in addressing the complexities of digitalisation and sustainable development. This year, researchers carried out 24 research exchanges (secondments) between emerging powers and Europe, solidifying PRODIGEES as a central hub for interdisciplinary and cross-border research.

International Research for Local and Global Challenges

IDOS

PRODIGEES (Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development) researchers tackled diverse issues through research exchanges, creating comparative perspectives that connect local and global challenges. Instituto Mora's Citlali Ayala and Isela Orihuela partnered with IDOS to explore the interplay between digitalisation and South-South cooperation on the one hand, and urban sustainability on the other. Regarding the latter, Isela Orihuela identified shared challenges in Mexico and Germany, such as bridging digital divides between rural and urban areas, integrating public services online, and aligning digital innovation with sustainable urban planning. Meanwhile, IDOS researcher, [Franco Luaregi](#), explored digitalisation's impact on urban mobility in a one-month secondment to Indonesia. The findings demonstrate how digitalisation can drive inclusive urban transformation.

From IDOS, [Dr Anita Breuer](#) expanded her analysis of digital disinformation by focusing on Brazil, building on her [earlier research in Mexico](#). Spending one month in Brazil, she investigated how digital platforms polarise societies and undermine democracy, offering critical insights to inform international policy recommendations. Also [Eva Lynders](#) and [Vy Dang](#) continued their investigations of digitalisation in connection to the G20/T20. After similar research in India last year, they implemented a secondment to FGV EBAPE in Rio de Janeiro.

In South Africa, Ingrid Schneider (University of Hamburg) advanced her comparative research on data protection regulations, continuing her work in Mexico, India, and Brazil. She examined how international frameworks influence local legislation and shaped the practical implementation of data governance. Her research identified opportunities for harmonisation while addressing existing gaps. Also four IDOS researchers, [Dr Sven Grimm](#), [Matthias Kachelmann](#), [Dr Wulf Reiners](#) and [Benjamin Stewart](#), implemented research secondments to Stellenbosch University with different thematic foci, including the science-policy interface.

Collaborative Policy Labs and Conference in South Africa

PRODIGEES coordinator, IDOS, and partner Stellenbosch University, co-hosted [Policy Labs in Stellenbosch and Cape Town](#), South Africa, which brought together experts from 14 institutions. Participants co-created policy solutions on ethical data governance, digital literacy, mitigating digitalisation's environmental impacts, and aligning with the UN's Global Digital Compact. Following a collaborative workshop design, the sessions successfully bridged academic expertise and practical policymaking.

Organised back-to-back to the Policy Labs, a joint Managing Global Governance (MGG) conference with the National School of Government of South Africa (NSG) focused on the interconnection of digitalisation and sustainable development with a particular view to capacity development in the civil service.

Ongoing Research Bridging Continents

PRODIGEES researchers continue to tackle digitalisation towards sustainable development from different perspectives. From South Africa, the University of Stellenbosch's Leanne Seeliger is analysing digital incentives to improve water conservation in Khayamandi Township while comparing these efforts with water management strategies in Germany. Meanwhile, during his research secondment to IDOS, Rifqi Rachman, from the Centre for Strategic and International Studies in Jakarta, is analysing how digital archives preserve collective memory.

Transforming Research Into Actionable Insights

PRODIGEES researchers are translating their work into accessible and creative formats. Rafaela Cavalcanti de Alcântara, from the Austrian Academy of Sciences - Institute of Technology Assessment (OEAW-ITA) in Vienna, created the fanzine [Inhabiting Body.territories](#), which vividly illustrates the intersections of data-driven urbanism and human embodiment.

You can find a full list of PRODIGEES publications, presentations, and digital knowledge products on the [PRODIGEES website](#) and download them from the [PRODIGEES Zenodo repository](#).

Looking Ahead

As 2024 concludes, PRODIGEES is preparing for its Final Conference, hosted by Instituto Mora in Mexico City from 9–13 March 2025. The project, which began in January 2020, will officially end on 30 June 2025.

Integration of mass transit systems: IDOS researcher's Fellowship at CSIS in Jakarta

By Newsletter | 23. Januar 2025 | Category: Allgemein

IDOS researcher and PhD candidate, **Franco Jauregui Fung**, undertook a research fellowship at the **Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS)** in Jakarta, Indonesia, during October and November 2024. The research focused on the integration of mass transit systems in Jakarta.

©Franco Jauregui Fung

As the city transitions from a bus rapid transit (BRT) network to railway services, the study emphasised integration at multiple levels—physical, digital, and fare-related—and examined its impact on the urban environment, particularly for transit-oriented development (TOD).

The fieldwork comprised two main components: interviews with local experts from public transport corporations, transport organisations, and real estate consultants, as well as visits to nine key intermodal stations. These stations were analysed to assess the integration of Transjakarta BRT stations with Jakarta's recently introduced rail services, including MRT Jakarta, LRT Jakarta, LRT Jabodebek, as well as the already existing KRL Commuter Line. These site visits provided valuable empirical data on multimodal integration and its effects on the surrounding urban environment. The dynamic nature of the fieldwork enhanced research skills in data collection, analysis, and cross-cultural communication. The experience also expanded professional networks and strengthened the focus on interdisciplinary research in sustainable urban mobility.

Franco Jauregui Fung presented his preliminary findings at the research seminar at CSIS Indonesia. This platform facilitated the sharing of insights into mass transit integration, opportunities for TOD, and the role of digital platforms in improving user experiences. The discussions with colleagues, many of whom are public transport users, offered meaningful perspectives that helped refine the analysis. The researcher also had the opportunity to attend the TOD Forum 2024, organised by PT MRT Jakarta. The event provided an opportunity to engage with leading experts and reflect on the importance of TOD in enhancing urban mobility. It also highlighted the critical role of design and architectural quality in creating spaces around mass transit stations not only to improve connectivity, but also to foster social cohesion.

©Franco Jauregui Fung

This fellowship offered first-hand exposure to Jakarta's significant progress in mass transit infrastructure and its positive impact on the urban environment. Engaging with local experts and witnessing the city's transformation into a transit-oriented city offered invaluable insights into the complexities of urban mobility in the Global South. The lessons learnt provide valuable guidance for other cities facing similar challenges, such as congestion and pollution from high levels of motorisation, while striving to enhance urban mobility. This opportunity has laid the groundwork for further research and collaboration, with the hope of returning to Jakarta in the future to witness the continued impact of these transformative changes.

The research fellowship is supported by the EU-funded project **PRODIGEES**, which focuses on sustainability, digitalisation, and transnational knowledge cooperation.

MGG/PRODIGEES Prepares for Its Final Conference in Mexico City

By Newsletter | 24. Februar 2025 | Category: Allgemein

The conference marks the culmination of five years of collaborative research within the Managing Global Governance (MGG) network, bringing together scholars, policymakers, and industry experts to explore the intersections of digitalisation and the economy, the environment, governance and society.

As the *Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development (PRODIGEES)* project approaches its conclusion, preparations are underway for its Final Conference, set to take place from 9 to 13 March 2025, at *Instituto Mora* in Mexico City.

In the lead-up to this milestone event, IDOS researchers [Benjamin Stewart](#), [Matthias Kachelmann](#) and [Dr Wulf Reiners](#) have embarked on a one-month secondment to Mexico, aligning their ongoing research with visits to network partners and conference preparations in close collaboration with Instituto Mora —a leading think tank, academic institute, core partner of MGG in Mexico, and PRODIGEES co-coordinator.

The MGG / PRODIGEES Final Conference will showcase insights from the project’s 74 research secondments conducted between 2020 and 2025, providing a platform for dialogue among experts from Mexico and the broader MGG Network. Participants will engage in discussions on how digitalisation can contribute to sustainable development, shaping future collaborations beyond the project’s official timeline.

More information about the MGG / PRODIGEES Final Conference can be found on the IDOS website: [IDOS Event Page](#)

Learn more about PRODIGEES at www.prodigees.info

All PRODIGEES publications, presentations, and digital knowledge products are open access and available via the [PRODIGEES Research Community on Zenodo](#)

POLICY INNOVATION LAB

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Reflecting on digitalisation in the public sector in Mexico City

Prof. Willem Fourie, lead of the Policy Innovation Lab, recently participated in the final conference of the PRODIGEES (Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development) project, held in Mexico City. The event marked the culmination of five years of international collaboration on the role of digital technologies in advancing sustainable development.

Prof. Fourie contributed to three sessions. In the first, he responded to a keynote address by Pablo Enrique Yanes Rizo, Secretary of Education, Science, Technology and Innovation for Mexico City. He highlighted the difficulty of crafting effective AI policies that balance the promotion of innovation with the need for risk mitigation.

The following day, he co-organised and participated in a workshop on "Digitalisation in the Public Sector". He was joined by representatives from the World Bank, Visor Urbano and the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS). Discussions focused on the complex nature of digital inclusion. While public interventions, such as those seen in India, have successfully reduced costs and expanded access, persistent barriers remain. These include the high cost of mobile data, particularly for marginalised groups, as well as issues related to trust, usability and accessibility for elderly and digitally excluded populations.

The workshop also addressed the digital skills gap in public administrations. Many governments face challenges in attracting and retaining skilled personnel. Participants agreed that for digital public infrastructure (DPI) to be effective, it must be open, trusted and underpinned by institutional models that blend internal capabilities with external innovation.

In the final session, Prof. Fourie joined a panel reflecting on the project's outcomes and future directions. He emphasised the critical role of citizen agency—not only in advocating for improved digital services, but also in how individuals engage as informed users of both public and private digital platforms.

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CSIS Indonesia, as part of the PRODIGEES Consortium, contributes to transnational knowledge sharing on this intersection by fostering long-term research partnerships between Europe and Brazil, India, Indonesia, Mexico, and South Africa through staff exchanges and network-wide activities.

PRODIGEES (Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development) is a project – jointly lead by the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) and the Mexican Instituto Mora – which is researching the effects of digitalisation on the environment, economy, governance and society. It sits on the cutting edge of research into digitalization and transnational knowledge cooperation.

The project is supported by the [European Union’s Horizon 2020](#) research program and [connects eight countries on five continents](#) in an investigation of digitalization’s social, governmental, economic, and climatic impacts from local, national, regional and global perspectives.

Digital technologies are among the most powerful enablers of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), but their success depends on social acceptance and their ability to foster sustainable and equitable growth. Understanding and shaping the interdependencies between digitalisation and sustainability is a key challenge in the digital era.

Some key highlights of the secondment are outlined below.

MGG/PRODIGEES Final Conference: Experts discussed digitalisation and sustainability

By Newsletter | 27. März 2025 | Category: Allgemein

The participants, consisting of researchers, policy-makers and practitioners, came together in Mexico City from 8 different countries across 5 continents to address pressing issues of digitalisation and sustainable development. The event highlighted key findings, policy recommendations and future collaborations.

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The MGG/PRODIGEES Final Conference, from 09 to 12 March 2025, was the concluding event of *Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development* (PRODIGEES), a five-year project funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 MSCA-RISE programme.

Embedded in the Managing Global Governance (MGG) network of IDOS and co-lead by IDOS and Instituto Mora (Mexico), the project facilitated comparative, transnational research on the intersection of digitalisation with governance, society, economy, and environment across Europe, Brazil, India, Indonesia, Mexico, and South Africa. The regions are facing distinct but interconnected challenges in balancing digital transformation with sustainable development.

The Final Conference provided a platform for participating researchers to present the project's publications, policy recommendations, future action plans, and training initiatives. The event also engaged a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers, academic institutions, civil society, and the general public to disseminate project results. Furthermore, a Memorandum of Understanding between IDOS and Instituto Mora was signed, following and sustaining the institutions' joint leadership in the project and their collaboration in organising the conference. In their laudation, representatives from both institutions highlighted the importance of acting towards sustainability on the local, national, and international levels while countering prevailing inequalities.

The participants explored and shared what they had learned from their own work with the PRODIGEES project. A wide set of conference sessions covered topics like information governance, digitalisation in science, the public sector, urban planning, and finance, and the environmental impact of AI. Reflective exchanges between participants took place through a range of interactive formats. These included a world café, where everyone could speak from their own contextual perspectives; a bar camp, where participants got the chance to present their own ideas and formats, and a gallery walk, during which the attendees discussed their impressions of paintings that addressed questions of sustainability and digitalisation. These formats offered the opportunity to learn about each other's work and share knowledge, so that participants could find many intersections and areas for potential collaborations.

On top of many substantive exchanges, the conference bore ample opportunities to share one's personal experiences with PRODIGEES or its related MGG programme. Many of the conference participants had been PRODIGEES researchers and conducted field research with other participating institutions. These exchanges had taken place throughout a total of 74 research and innovation secondments. In addition, many other conference attendees had formerly participated in IDOS' MGG Academy or knowledge cooperation and policy dialogue formats.

Accompanying this milestone event, IDOS researchers [Benjamin Stewart](#), [Matthias Kachelmann](#), and [Dr Wulf Reiners](#) embarked on a one-month secondment to Mexico, aligning their ongoing research with visits to network partners and conference preparations in close collaboration with Instituto Mora.

